

XORIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC PROPERTIES OF PHARMACEUTICAL TERMS

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Abstract. *This article examines the structural and semantic properties of pharmaceutical terms. It also analyzes the factor of expansion of terminology of a particular area of pharmacy.*

Key words: *structural and semantic properties, pharmaceutical terms, expansion factors, areas of pharmacy, terminological system.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada farmatsevtik atamalarning tarkibiy va semantik xususiyatlarini tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, u farmatsiyaning ma'lum bir sohasi terminologiyasini kengaytirish omilini tahlil qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *tarkibiy va semantik xususiyatlar, farmatsevtik atamalar, kengayish omillari, farmatsevtika sohalari, terminologiya tizimi.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются структурно-семантические свойства фармацевтических терминов. А также анализируется фактором расширения терминологии той или иной области фармации.*

Ключевые слова: *структурно-семантические свойства, фармацевтических термины, факторы расширения, области фармации, терминосистема.*

Description and analysis of specialized terminology systems is one of the leading areas of linguistic research in recent decades. Increased interest in issues of special nomination is explained by the growing role of terminology, its standardization in various fields of knowledge. In order to achieve a single designation and understanding of entities and processes of the surrounding world, as well as to maximize the effectiveness of the activities of specialists in various fields of science and production, issues of unification and harmonization of terminology are being developed.

The effectiveness of the study of specialized terminology systems consists in the extent to which its results make a certain contribution to the development of the theory of nomination, onomasiology, and to the study of the linguistic picture of the world. The mechanism of term formation and the organization of the terminology system depend not only on the experience accumulated in the study of terminology systems, but also on the level of development of the corresponding field of knowledge, that is, it is due to social and economic reasons.

Pharmacy in our country is currently such an area of practice and science that is developing especially dynamically. Specialists working in the pharmaceutical

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industry - scientists, practitioners, pharmacy workers, control services, managers, as well as students of pharmaceutical universities and faculties - all use the terminology of pharmacy. Today, a pharmacy is both a social institution of health care, connected with the life and well-being of each person, designed to show mercy to the patient, and a business that provides for its profitability. In this regard, it can be assumed that the terminological system of pharmacy, like any lexical formation, on the one hand, historically develops, improves, that is, is in constant historical development. On the other hand, the terminology of pharmacy today is a fixed set of concepts, therefore, its current state can be analyzed in order to detect and record in it possible specific phenomena characteristic of this, the present stage of its formation.

According to one of the leading terminologists of our country V.F.Novodranova, in the formation of the terminology of any science, two stages can be distinguished: 1) the initial, natural stage and 2) conscious, regulated. The terminology system of pharmacy is no exception. Pharmaceutical terminology is a set of terms associated with the corresponding system of concepts of the pharmaceutical industry. Historically, it was formed based on various sources. Thus, many basic pharmaceutical terms are borrowed from Greek and Latin. At a later time, terms for it were borrowed from such border scientific areas as chemistry, biology, medicine or created on a national basis by attracting terms from other sources. Currently, the structure of the pharmacy sphere as an object of study from the point of view of scientific and practical activities of future specialists is a kind of framework of its constituent basic sciences: drug technology, pharmacology, pharmaceutical chemistry, economics, pharmacognosy and their integration aspects. According to I.M.Pertsev, as well as other researchers, pharmaceutical terminology is not isomorphic enough (Greek isos - equal, identical, similar; morphe - type, form). The reason lies in its reliance on a number of independently developed terminologies.

Firstly, this is chemical terminology, which is an example of an isomorphic nomenclature terminology system of chemical compounds, for example, potassium bromide (Kalii bromidum).

Secondly, this is the botanical binary nomenclature classification system of plants by the Swedish botanist K. Linnaeus (1753), which includes the name of the genus (the first word) and the species epithet (the second word). The name of K. Linnaeus in the botanical name is designated by the letter L. The names of other authors are also rendered in abbreviations, for example, purple coneflower - *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench.

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Thirdly, pharmacognostic terminology, including the names of pharmacognostic (Greek - pharmakon + gnosis - knowledge) objects (plant organs, products of plant and animal origin), for example, rhizomes with roots of valerian - *Rhizomata cum radicibus Valerianae*.

Fourthly, the terminology of pharmaceutical chemistry, including the synthesis, properties and analysis of medicinal substances. For example, the class of natural compounds xanthones comes from the Greek xanthos - yellow, denoting substances of yellow color.

Fifthly, technological terminology, representing the theoretical foundations, schemes and methods of pharmacy and production operations for the preparation of drugs, for example, sterilize (from Latin sterilisare), suppositories (Latin suppositoria).

Sixthly, pharmacological terminology, which includes the classification of drugs of various pharmacotherapeutic groups, reflecting their therapeutic effect. For example, the group of drugs "Antibiotics" - from ancient Greek anti- against + ancient Greek bios life - are organic substances that suppress the growth and development of certain microbes.

Seventh, the terminology of other medical and biological scientific fields, which are a reflection of the existence of certain intersecting areas in the science of pharmacy, where information obtained through various channels "meets". These connections are becoming increasingly obvious and necessary lately, when new branches appear at the intersection of sciences and, as a consequence, their names, such as pharmacoconomics, pharmacoepidemiology, pharma-logistics, biotechnology, ecopharmacy, nanotechnology, etc. Thus, even the above examples of the names of certain disciplines are reference terms for the movement of scientific thought, since they reflect the prospects for the integration of certain disciplines.

An example of a historically closed and spontaneously formed terminological system is the terminology of homeopathy, which can be attributed to the field of drug technology, pharmaceutical terminology. The linguistic material of this science has not been sufficiently studied, but a striking feature of it is the presence of names of drugs in scientific and educational literature formed by transliteration of Latin names of plants, animals, chemical compounds, etc. At the same time, examples of chemical, botanical nomenclatures are an example of names created according to regular models. They allow us to reveal the orientational capabilities of language through their expression of generic connections and relationships, and they, in turn, are responsible for the implementation of the process of cognition. Along with this, it

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should be noted that the development of practical needs of life was an incentive for the appearance on the pharmaceutical market of new exotic plants and preparations from them, for example, ginkgo biloba L., one of the oldest relict plants on Earth, from which the preparations "Bilo-bil", "Ginkgo forte" are produced. Thus, not only the educational and scientific discipline was replenished with new terms, but also the nomenclature of raw materials and drugs. Another factor in the expansion of the terminology of a particular area of pharmacy is the active introduction of Anglicisms, which can be observed partly in the terminology of pharmaceutical chemistry and to a large extent - in the terminology of management and economics of pharmacy. Thus, in scientific articles, along with the original term for the substance cholesterol, its English version cholesterol is increasingly encountered (instead of glycerin - glycerol, instead of phytosterol - phytosterol, etc.). We are talking, as we understand, about the same substances, only in different countries different components of the chemical composition are reflected in the process of verbalization of this concept. In the first example (cholesterol - cholesterol) we are talking about the main component of bile. In the term cholesterol, the element ster denotes a solid consistency + the suffix -in indicates the chemical composition, and in the second - cholesterol - the suffix -ol fixes the presence of an alcohol group in the substance. The intensive introduction of such terms into pharmaceutical terminology creates a duplicate, an unjustified, in our opinion, synonymy.

In addition, changes in the terminology of pharmacy are associated not only with the accumulation of purely objective scientific data, but also with the entire course of development of practical needs of life. Thus, in the terminology fund of the science of pharmacology for many years there was a term to designate a group of drugs with a calming effect - the so-called tranquilizers (from the Latin tranquillare - to calm). Medicines of the discussed group have the ability not only to calm, but also to relieve the feeling of fear, which has been especially relevant in recent years. The emphasis on this mechanism of action on a person created the conditions and pushed for the gradual transformation of the name of this group of drugs to anxiolytics (from the Latin anxius - inspiring fear, anxious + lysis - destruction, dissolution), thereby enriching pharmacology with a new term. Thus, the terminology of pharmacoeconomics is currently experiencing the peak of its development, since it reflects its dependence on the factors that determine the economy or politics of modern Russian society. Foreign economic terminology, mainly English words and expressions, must be considered as a reality in the language of modern pharmacy.

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Linguists notice and record such innovations in the language, which allows them to further explain the new version of the professional language of pharmacy.

Summarizing all of the above, we can come to the following conclusions. The language of pharmacy, its terminology serves various areas of pharmaceutical activity. In the current period of pharmacy development, a natural process of rethinking its terms is taking place, since the idea of activity directly in the field of pharmacy itself is developing, changing and expanding. The discussed language processes (neologization, hybridization, abbreviation, etc.) occur in the language of pharmacy exclusively under the influence of extra-linguistic factors (socio-political, economic).

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